

N-*p*-Tolyl Oxamic Acid as Analytical Reagent for Uranyl [UO₂(II)]

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N-*p*-tolyl oxamic acid (NPTOXA) has been successfully used as an analytical reagent for gravimetric estimation of UO₂(II) and its separation, using a number of masking agents from some metal ions resulting from the radioactive disintegration and consequently occurring in uranium ores.

GUPTA *et al*¹ carried out the studies on the application of α -naphthyl oxamic acid as analytical reagent for some transition metal ions. Sharma *et al*² applied *m*-toluidinyl oxamic acid for the gravimetric separation of some lanthanides from a number of metal ions. These studies have been extended with *p*-toluidinyl oxamic acid³, which has been successfully employed for the estimation of common transition metal ions. In the present communication the authors describe a detailed study on the application of *p*-toluidinyl oxamic acid or N-*p*-tolyl oxamic acid (NPTOXA) as a gravimetric reagent for the estimation and separation of dioxouranium(VI) ion from some common metal ions usually present in uranium ores.

Experimental

Solutions of dioxouranium(VI) nitrate, copper(II) nitrate, nickel(II) nitrate, lead(II) nitrate, bismuth(III) nitrate and thorium(IV) nitrate were prepared by dissolving AR BDH materials in double distilled water. The metal contents of the solutions were determined by standard methods and solutions of desired concentrations were prepared by subsequent dilution of the stock solutions.

N-*p*-tolyl oxamic acid was prepared and purified by crystallisation (m. p. 162° ± 1) by the method described by Chaturvedi *et al*³. Solutions of NPTOXA of the required concentrations were prepared by dissolving requisite amount of crystallised acid in 60% ethanol.

The pH measurements were carried out with precision Philips pH-meter (PR 9405), standardised against 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate for pH = 4 at 25 ± 1°.

Method :

Stoichiometry of UO₂²⁺-NPTOXA chelate : The stoichiometry of UO₂²⁺-NPTOXA chelate (1 : 2) was established by potentiometric titration and further substantiated by isolating and analysing the chelate.

10 ml (0.025M) UO₂(NO₃)₂ solution was precipitated by adding a slight excess of (0.025M)

NPTOXA solution at pH 4 (adjusted by adding dilute KOH). The light yellow flocculent precipitate formed was filtered through a sintered glass crucible and washed repeatedly with distilled water and finally with 60% ethanol. It was dried at 110° for 3 to 4 hrs to a constant weight. The UO₂(II) compound was found to be insoluble in ethanol, acetone, chloroform, benzene.

Uranium in the above compound was estimated as U₃O₈ and nitrogen by Dumas method. The analysis confirmed the 1 : 2 metal : ligand ratio as found out potentiometrically.

The results of analysis are recorded below

	Found (%)	Calculated (%) for the proposed formula*
Uranium	38.10	38.00
Nitrogen	4.38	4.47

where R = CH₃ - C₆H₄ - NH -
Proposed formula*

Gravimetric estimations :

pH studies : The estimation of UO₂²⁺ was carried out at different pH in order to find out the optimum pH for quantitative precipitation of the metal ion. The results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

pH	mg of UO ₂ ²⁺ taken	mg of the UO ₂ ²⁺ -chelate	Calculated (mg) of UO ₂ ²⁺ from the UO ₂ ²⁺ chelate	% Error
3.0	270.0	622.8	268.5	-0.5
4.0	270.0	625.8	269.7	-0.11
6.0	270.0	624.8	269.3	-0.25

Concentration of UO₂(NO₃)₂ = 0.1M

From the results recorded in Table 1, it is evident that the quantitative precipitation of the UO₂²⁺

TABLE 2

UO ₂ ²⁺ taken (mg)	UO ₂ (C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃) ₂ obtained (mg)	UO ₂ ²⁺ calculated from complex (mg)	% Error
135.0	313.0	134.8	-0.14
270.0	625.8	269.7	-0.11

Concentration of UO₂(NO₃)₂ = 0.1M

agents the quantitative separation of UO₂²⁺ from some of these ions including those often occurring in uranium ores, as well as the metals formed during radioactive decay of uranium could be accomplished with success. The results of the quantitative separation of UO₂²⁺ as (C₉H₈NO₃)₂UO₂ from the ions referred are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Diverse ions (mg)	Masking agent	UO ₂ ²⁺ taken (mg)	UO ₂ (C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃) ₂ formed (mg)	UO ₂ ²⁺ calculated in UO ₂ (C ₉ H ₈ NO ₃) ₂ (mg)	% Error
Cu ²⁺	CN ⁻	67.50	156.40	67.42	-0.11
		135.00	312.60	134.76	-0.17
Ni ²⁺	CN ⁻	67.50	156.20	67.34	-0.23
		135.00	312.80	134.80	-0.14
Pb ²⁺	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	67.50	156.20	67.34	-0.23
		135.00	312.80	134.80	-0.14
Bi ³⁺	S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	67.50	156.40	67.42	-0.11
		135.00	312.80	134.80	-0.14
Th ⁴⁺	CN ⁻	67.50	156.40	67.42	-0.11
		135.00	312.40	134.68	-0.23

Concentration of UO₂(NO₃)₂ = 0.025M KCN Solution (1%); Hypo Solution (10%)

ion occurs at pH 4.0. In all the estimations the pH for the precipitation of the chelate was maintained at 4.0.

Estimation of UO₂²⁺ as UO₂(C₉H₈NO₃)₂: Ethanolic solution of the reagent (NPTOXA) was added slowly with constant stirring to different aliquotes of UO₂(NO₃)₂ solution diluted previously with distilled water. After complete precipitation the chelate was digested on water bath for about half an hour, cooled to room temperature and filtered through sintered glass crucible (G 4), washed repeatedly with cold distilled water followed by 60% ethanol. It was finally dried at 110° and weighed as UO₂(C₉H₈NO₃)₂.

The results of the estimation are recorded in the Table 2.

Estimation of UO₂²⁺ in presence of diverse ions: NPTOXA is found to form flocculant easily filtrable precipitates with a number of transition and non-transition metal ions. Using appropriate masking

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